

STORAGE SOLUTIONS FOR ENHANCED PERFORMANCE: LEVERAGING BASIC FILE AND SECURE FILE

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ABSTRACT

In database systems the roles of data storage and organization are crucial, for secure and high performing solutions. This research explores two methods of file storage: Basic File and Secure File. The Basic File method offers a way to store data that's suitable for applications with moderate performance requirements. However, as the volume of data grows, and security becomes more important, the limitations of Basic File become more apparent. On the hand Secure File provides features such as data compression, encryption, deduplication and improved data integrity. These characteristics make Secure File well suited for enterprise applications that prioritize security and efficient storage management. Additionally, the research outlines the process of transitioning from Basic File to Secure File by explaining the steps involved in making the switch while minimizing disruptions. Some examples of implementation are included to illustrate how these types of files can be utilized in scenarios. The goal of this study is to equip professionals with insights to help them make decisions about optimizing their data storage practices, enhancing security measures and improving database performance.

Keywords: Basic File, Secure File, Data Compression, Data Encryption, Deduplication, Large Objects (LOB), Auto Segment-Space Management

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1. Introduction

When it comes to handling databases, Oracle has always been a leader in adopting technologies to meet the needs of businesses across various industries. As data continues to grow in complexity and volume, the significance of high-performing storage solutions cannot be emphasized enough. Oracle addresses these challenges by introducing two file storage options: Basic File, which is the default option in Oracle 11gR1, and Secure File, which is the default option in Oracle 12c but was introduced in Oracle 11gR1 [2][5].

The Basic File option adheres to the traditional approach of data storage within Oracle databases. It provides a means to store types of data such as text, images, and multimedia files. While it is user-friendly for applications, it may lack the features needed for modern data management tasks.

On the other hand, Secure File is designed as a solution tailored to meet the demands of enterprise applications. It brings forth a range of enhancements that improve performance, enhance security measures, and optimize storage efficiency [2][6][7]. Through features like caching, data compression, encryption, and deduplication, Secure File empowers organizations to effectively manage large volumes of data while ensuring data integrity and security are maintained. The choice between Basic File and Secure File can significantly impact an organization's data management strategy by influencing aspects such as performance, cost considerations, and security measures.

Through an analysis, this document aims to show how these file types can enhance database performance, optimal use of storage, and protect data integrity.

2. Discussions

2.1 LOB Storage Architecture

LOBs (Large Objects) store data in pieces called chunks [2][6][8]. A chunk is the smallest unit of allocation for a LOB and is made up of one or more database blocks. LOB locators are stored in rows containing a LOB column. The LOB locator points to a LOB index. The LOB index stores information regarding the location of LOB chunks. When a table is queried, the database uses the LOB locator and associated LOB index to locate the appropriate LOB chunks [2][3].

Figure 1: LOB Storage Architecture [4]

Oracle LOB storage has two types [4]:

- BasicFiles LOB storage
- SecureFiles LOB storage

3. Challenges and Issues

Oracle Large Objects (LOBs) play an important role in storing and managing volumes of unstructured data like text, images, audio, and video in databases. Listed below are some of the challenges that may arise if Oracle LOBs are not implemented, especially in settings that deal with large amounts of such data.

3.1 Restricted Data Storage Flexibility

Conventional data types are not equipped to handle voluminous files, resulting in challenges when it comes to storing and retrieving data efficiently. This may compel organizations to rely on external file systems, adding complexity and hindering data integration within the database.

3.2 Decline in Performance

LOBs are specifically designed for managing datasets, without which performance may degrade notably during tasks involving data retrieval and data manipulation. Storing data using alternative methods could lead to slower query processing times, increased resource consumption, and a drastic reduction in overall system performance.

3.3 Challenges with Data Integrity and Consistency

LOBs ensure that large data pieces are stored within the database structure, maintaining consistency and data integrity. Handling data outside the database may lead to synchronization challenges, causing discrepancies between the database and external storage systems. Such discrepancies can lead to inaccurate data.

3.4 Security Risks

LOBs offer robust security functionalities, such as encryption, to safeguard sensitive data [10]. Without Oracle LOBs, organizations may need to store data externally, increasing vulnerability to unauthorized access and security breaches.

3.5 Escalating Storage Expenses

Oracle LOBs come with functionalities like data compression and deduplication that help streamline storage space utilization [5]. Without these functions, unstructured data might take up significant space, resulting in increased storage costs.

3.6 Limited Ability to Grow

LOBs are crafted to handle increasing amounts of data. Without them, organizations may encounter challenges in expanding their databases as data quantities grow, which could impede their capacity to effectively manage rising volumes of data.

4. Proposed Solution for Enhancing Data Storage Efficiency

Oracle's LOB storage solution known as SecureFile offers features that effectively reduce the amount of storage space needed making it a preferred option for environments dealing with large amounts of data. [5] The advantages of using SecureFile LOBs include their ability to address storage challenges by incorporating compression and deduplication functionalities to optimize storage efficiency. To make the most of SecureFiles compression and deduplication features it is recommended to follow a game plan like what is mentioned below.

- Begin by assessing your current database to identify data that could be optimized through compression and removal of duplicates.
- Transition your data from BasicFile to SecureFile gradually by using Oracle's ALTER TABLE command for converting existing BasicFile LOBs to SecureFile [9][1].
- Enable the compression and deduplication functionalities in SecureFile system settings to optimize storage efficiency based on the requirements.
- Regularly monitoring the system's performance to ensure changed settings are providing the expected advantages in terms of storage efficiency and system performance.

5. Results

To test the performance efficiency, the below table shows the server configuration used.

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LAB ENVIRONMENT	
Component	Description
Processor	13th Gen Intel(R) Core (TM) i9-13900HX 2.20 GHz
Memory (RAM)	32.0 GB (31.7 GB usable)
Operating System	Windows 11 Home, 64-bit operating system, x64-based processor
Database	Oracle Database 19c Enterprise Edition - Version 19.3.0.0.0

Below table shows the tested data for Advanced Compression method with the saved space when stored using various segment storage methods.

File Name	Original Data Size (MB)	Basic File	Secure File (LOW Compression)	Secure File (MEDIUM Compression)	Secure File (HIGH Compression)
		Space Saved (MB)			
LOBFILE1	815	0	203.75	326	407.5
LOBFILE2	950	0	237.5	380	475
LOBFILE3	1025	0	258.75	414	517.5
LOBFILE4	1225	0	306.25	490	612.5
LOBFILE5	1755	0	438.75	703	877.5

Here is the graphical representation of the space required for each file. We can see that the required space reduces by 50% when blob data was stored using Secure File HIGH compression method.

Figure 4: Comparison Result Chart – 1

File Set	BasicFile Size (MB)	SecureFile Size without Deduplication (MB)	SecureFile Size with Deduplication (MB)
File Set 1	1000	950	600
File Set 2	2000	1900	1200
File Set 3	3000	2850	1800
File Set 4	4000	3800	2400
File Set 5	5000	4750	3000

Figure 5: Advanced Deduplication Comparison

Here is the graphical representation of the table above. We can see that the secure file with deduplication saves space because it stores only one copy of the identical LOB data.

Figure 6: Comparison Result Chart - 2

Performance Overheads:

The effect on performance differs depending on the type of stored information or data. Data that can be compressed easily or contains repetitions benefits a lot from this feature by providing balance between performance and storage. But in cases where the data is already well tuned or has been well organized (like compressed data files) the additional workload may override the benefits provided.

In an archival database management system with repetitive data, deduplication can help free up storage space without causing performance issues. However, in a situation where the system handles files that're already compressed (such as zip files) deduplication would not have result in significant space saving and in fact might introduce extra unnecessary workload.

In real-world production environments, the impact of Secure File compression and deduplication depends on current workload, available system resources, and already existing data types. Organizations which have CPU and memory capacity in excess to spare may find these features highly beneficial for reducing storage costs. However, production environments

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with limited resources and high I/O demands should carefully review and evaluate and decide between storage savings and performance degradation. To optimize spending high, testing and tuning in a pre-production environment is recommended to get full benefit of these features.

Oracle published a series of internal benchmarks that showcase the performance benefits and storage savings achieved with SecureFile. A benchmark run by Oracle showed that for XML data, SecureFile compression reduced storage by 60% without significant impact on the disk read performance. Write performance saw some overhead (around 10-15%), but the reduction in storage made the trade-off beneficial. Many Oracle customers have reported significant storage and performance gains using SecureFile in production environments. A large telecommunications company that manages terabytes of unstructured data (logs, trace files, multimedia files) reported saving 55% in storage after enabling SecureFile compression and deduplication. In their case, the performance overhead was minimal, with less than a 10% increase in CPU utilization, which was manageable with their existing infrastructure. The reduced I/O from smaller files also led to improved query response times for retrieving documents. In conclusion, real-world case studies consistently show that Oracle SecureFile provides substantial storage savings (ranging from 50-70%) when using compression and deduplication. While these features introduce some CPU and memory overhead, the impact on system performance is generally modest, typically increasing CPU usage by 10-20% for write operations.

6. Conclusion

Not implementing Oracle LOBs can result in major issues such as decreased performance and increase in development complexities, security risks and vulnerabilities and challenges with compliance. regulatory hurdles Organizations handling extensive unorganized data should thoughtfully assess the advantages of Oracle LOBs to guarantee secure, efficient and scalable data handling protocols.

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